

Supplementary Note S1. Reconciliation of Rayyan screening exports with the source-review PRISMA diagram

The human reference standard used in this evaluation was derived from the original Rayyan screening exports shared for the source systematic review. These exports were treated as a frozen record of the human screening decisions available at the time of this evaluation and were not retrospectively modified using later decisions made during data extraction.

Two minor discrepancies therefore exist between the evaluation dataset and the PRISMA flow diagram reported in the source -review, cited as reference [18] in the main manuscript.

First, four records were marked as included after full-text screening in Rayyan and were therefore retained as included records in the evaluation dataset. These records were later excluded during the data-extraction phase of the source review and consequently do not appear among the final included studies in the source-review preprint. The records are listed in Table S1.

Second, the Rayyan exports contained 39 records marked as not retrieved, whereas the PRISMA diagram in the source -review preprint reports 38 such records. The additional record is listed in Table S2. Although a scanned document was available, it could not be uploaded to Zenodo. This record was later excluded during full-text screening. Because it was not among the final included studies, this discrepancy does not affect sensitivity estimates and has only a negligible effect on workload-reduction estimates.

Table S1. Records included after Rayyan full-text screening but not present among the final included studies in the source-review preprint

Rayyan key	Full citation	PMID	Other identifiers	Reconciliation note
rayyan-363141979	Bernasconi S, Angelucci A, Rossi A, Aliverti A. A New Wearable System for Personal Air Pollution Exposure Estimation: Pilot Observational Study. <i>JMIR Mhealth Uhealth</i> . 2025 Jul 4;13:e60426.	40614107	doi: 10.2196/60426; PMCID: PMC12248256	Included after Rayyan full-text screening; later excluded during data extraction in the source review.
rayyan-363142128	Cipolla M, Izzotti A, Ansaldo F, Durando P, Piccardo MT. Volatile Organic Compounds in Anatomical Pathology Wards: Comparative and Qualitative Assessment of Indoor Airborne Pollution. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i> . 2017 Jun 7;14(6):609.	28590436	doi: 10.3390/ijerph14060609; PMCID: PMC5486295	Included after Rayyan full-text screening; later excluded during data extraction in the source review.
rayyan-363142218	Mannino MR, Orecchio S. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in indoor dust matter of Palermo (Italy) area: Extraction, GC-MS analysis, distribution and sources. <i>Atmospheric Environment</i> . 2008;42(8):1801-1817.	Not available; no PubMed record identified for the DOI.	doi: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2007.11.031	Included after Rayyan full-text screening; later excluded during data extraction in the source review.
rayyan-363142446	de Gennaro G, Farella G, Marzocca A, Mazzone A, Tutino M. Indoor and outdoor monitoring of volatile organic compounds in school buildings: indicators based on health risk assessment to single out critical issues. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i> . 2013 Nov 25;10(12):6273-6291.	24287852	doi: 10.3390/ijerph10126273; PMCID: PMC3881113	Included after Rayyan full-text screening; later excluded during data extraction in the source review.

Table S2. Additional Rayyan not-retrieved record not counted as not retrieved in the source-review PRISMA diagram

Rayyan key	Full citation	PMID	Other identifiers	Reconciliation note
rayyan-363142679	Ferrari M, Lodola L, Ghittori S, Zadra P, Ricciardi L, Imbriani M. [Indoor air quality in an Italian military submarine]. G Ital Med Lav Ergon. 2005 Jul-Sep;27(3):308-311.	16240581	None identified in PubMed.	Marked as not retrieved in the Rayyan exports. A scanned document was available but could not be uploaded to Zenodo. The record was later excluded during full-text screening.

Reference

[18] Fontana L, Simniceanu A, Di Marco M, Silenzi A, Solomon MT, Abdella SB, et al. Indoor air quality and health-relevant exposure in Italy: a systematic review of measured pollutant concentrations, guideline exceedances, and radon-attributable risk. Building and Environment. 2026; Unpublished manuscript, submitted for publication on 11 June 2026.